

NONLINEAR AND DAMAGE BEHAVIOR OF CERAMIC-MATRIX CROSS-PLY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the damage evolution of Nicalon fiber reinforced calcium alumino-silicate glass (SiC/CAS) cross-ply composites. Both transverse cracking in the 90° plies and matrix cracking in the 0° plies have been studied. Energy balance methods and shear-lag models are adopted in this investigation. Closed-form solutions for critical stresses of matrix cracking have been found for two limiting cases: perfect bonding and fiber/matrix interfacial sliding. The effect of thermal residual stresses has been taken into account. The composite nonlinear stress-strain relations are predicted and compared with experimental measurements. The sources of discrepancies between theoretical and experimental results at strains greater than 0.2% have been identified.

Keywords: ceramic-matrix composite, matrix cracking, damage, nonlinear behavior

1. INTRODUCTION

Numerous models have been proposed in recent years for studying the initiation of matrix cracks in unidirectional brittle matrix composites. Aveston, Cooper and Kelly (1971) adopted a fiber bridging model and obtained a closed-form solution for the critical strain of matrix cracking [1]. The fiber/matrix interface was assumed to be completely debonded. Budiansky et al. introduced the concept of steady-state cracking, assuming that crack growth proceeds without the increase in applied stress [2]. They examined the effect of perfect bonding and sliding conditions of interface on steady-state cracking. Marshall et al. treated the cracking problem as a mode-I fracture and allowed the initial matrix crack to have arbitrary sizes [3]. The fibers, which bridge the crack surfaces, are replaced by an equivalent traction continuously distributed on the surfaces.

Multiple cracking in cross-ply composites has also received a great deal of attention from researchers [4-7]. All these works, however, focused on the behavior of polymer matrix composites, in which multiple cracking was attributed to the transverse cracking in 90° plies.

For the SiC/CAS cross-ply composites tested under tension, transverse cracks appear first in 90° plies, and as the transverse crack density increases with loading to a certain level, matrix cracks bridged by the fiber appear in 0° plies [8]. The matrix crack density in 0° plies can often be higher than the transverse crack density in 90° plies at high strain levels. Interactions between transverse and matrix cracks may exist; this is a unique behavior of brittle matrix cross-ply composites.

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In this paper, the term *matrix cracking* is used to describe the steady-state separation of matrix with fiber bridging in the 0° plies of cross-ply composites. The term *transverse cracking* is used only to indicate the cracking in 90° plies. Furthermore, we define *major crack* to be a matrix crack plus a transverse crack at the same cross-section and *minor crack* to be a matrix crack without a connecting transverse crack. Examples of major and minor cracks are shown in Fig. 1.

2. CRITICAL STRESSES FOR MATRIX CRACKING

The cross-ply composite is considered to be composed of three entities, i.e. the 90° ply, the fiber in the 0° ply and the matrix in the 0° ply. Stress distributions in these three entities are obtained by using a shear-lag method by the authors [9-11]. Then, an energy balance method is adopted to determine the condition for matrix cracking. The energy terms involved in creating matrix cracking include (1) strain energy changes in these entities, (2) matrix surface energy, (3) fiber/matrix frictional sliding energy, and (4) work done by the external load. Due to the fact that most CMCs have weak fiber/matrix bonding, the fiber/matrix debonding energy (or interfacial fracture toughness) has been neglected in this paper. The details of the stress distributions and energy terms can be found in Refs. 10 and 11.

The first case studied is matrix cracking in a major crack with perfect fiber/matrix bonding as shown in Fig. 2a. The critical stress for this case has been obtained in the following closed-form solution:

$$\sigma_{cr1} = \frac{b}{b+d} \left(\frac{4\beta}{3} \frac{\gamma_m E_1 E_f V_f}{E_m} \right)^{1/2} - \frac{b}{b+d} E_1 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_m) \Delta T \quad (1)$$

The second case is matrix cracking in a major crack with fiber/matrix debonding as shown in Fig. 2b, and the corresponding critical stress is

$$\sigma_{cr2} = \frac{b}{b+d} \left(\frac{12 \tau_i \gamma_m E_1^2 E_f V_f^2}{r_o V_m E_m^2} \right)^{1/3} - \frac{b}{b+d} E_1 (\alpha_1 - \alpha_m) \Delta T \quad (2)$$

In Eqs. (1) and (2), r_o is fiber radius, τ_i is interfacial shear stress, and γ_m is matrix surface energy. The symbols E , V , and α represent modulus, volume fraction, and thermal expansion coefficient, respectively. b is the thickness of the 0°-ply, and d is the half-thickness of the 90° ply as indicated in Fig. 2. The subscripts f , m and l stand for fiber, matrix and longitudinal direction, respectively. The shear-lag constant β in Eq. (1) is [9-11]

$$\beta = \left[\frac{8}{r_o^2} \left(\frac{1}{G_f} + \frac{1}{G_m} \left(\frac{2}{V_m^2} \ln \frac{1}{V_f} - 3 - \frac{2V_f}{V_m} \right) \right)^{-1} \frac{E_1}{E_f E_m V_m} \right]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

Here, G denotes the shear modulus. Both the fiber and matrix shear deformations have been taken into account in Eq. (4).

3. CRACK DENSITIES

Experimental observations indicate that transverse cracks occur in 90° plies, followed by matrix cracks in 0° plies. Schematic representation of damage configurations has been shown in Fig. 1. The crack spacings in 0° and 90° plies are denoted as L_1 and L_2 respectively. The crack density (ρ) is defined as the number of cracks per unit length. Therefore, the relation between crack spacing and crack density can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_1 &= \frac{1}{L_1} \\ \rho_2 &= \frac{1}{L_2}\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

The ratio of crack densities in 0° and 90° plies, denoted as ϕ , is defined as follows:

$$\phi = \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2} = \frac{L_2}{L_1}\quad (5)$$

Experimental results of crack densities for $[0_3/90/0_3]$ and $[0_3/90_3/0_3]$ SiC/CAS composites can be seen in Fig. 3.

4. COMPOSITE STRESS-STRAIN RELATIONS

The composite stress-strain relation deviates from the initial linearity after either transverse cracks or matrix cracks form in the composite. To study the composite stress-strain relation, the strain for each case shown in Fig. 1 is evaluated. Since the elongation of the composite is identical to that of the fibers in the 0° plies, the composite strain is equal to the average fiber strain, which can be obtained by the shear-lag method. In debonded regions, a constant frictional stress (τ_i) is assumed, and the debonding length is denoted as L_d . To simplify the problem, the fiber/matrix debonding lengths are assumed to be identical for both major and minor cracks. The results of composite strains, ϵ_c , for $\phi = 0$ through 3 are as follows:

$$\epsilon_c^0 = \frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} + \frac{dE_2}{bE_1} \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{E_c} + (\alpha_c - \alpha_1) \Delta T \right) \frac{2}{\lambda L_2} \tanh \left(\frac{\lambda L_2}{2} \right)\quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_c^1 &= \frac{1}{E_f} \left\{ \sigma_A \left(1 - \frac{L_d}{L_2} \right) - (\sigma_A - \sigma_{f_0}) \cdot \right. \\ &\quad \left[1 - \frac{2L_d}{L_2} - \frac{2}{\lambda L_2} \tanh \lambda \left(\frac{L_2}{2} - L_d \right) \right] + \frac{L_d}{L_2} \frac{b+d}{bV_f} \sigma_c \left. \right\} \\ &\quad + (\alpha_f - \alpha_1) \Delta T\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon_c^2 = \epsilon_c^1 + \Delta \epsilon\quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon_c^3 = \epsilon_c^2 + \Delta \epsilon\quad (9)$$

The superscript in Eqs. (6-9) stands for the value of ϕ , and

$$\lambda = \left[\frac{3G_{13}G_{23}}{bG_{23} + dG_{13}} \frac{bE_1 + dE_2}{bdE_1E_2} \right]^{1/2}$$

$$\sigma_A = \frac{b+d}{bV_f} \sigma_c - \frac{2L_d}{r_o} \tau_i$$

$$\sigma_{f_0} = \frac{E_f}{E_1} \sigma_c + E_f (\alpha_1 - \alpha_f) \Delta T$$

$$\Delta \epsilon = \frac{bE_m V_m}{(bE_f V_f + dE_2)E_c} \frac{2L_d}{L_2} \sigma_c - \frac{2L_d^2}{r_o L_2} \frac{bV_f}{d+bV_f} \frac{\tau_i}{E_f}$$

Equations (6) - (9) are composite strains corresponding to the damage modes shown in Fig. 1, in which ϕ is assumed to be integers, and the cracks are assumed to be evenly distributed. However, the crack densities increase continuously with composite strain, and ϕ also varies continuously. To simulate this, it is assumed that the composite is composed of two unit cells with $\phi=n$ and $\phi=n+1$, with n being an integer. We adopt the idea of interpolation to obtain the composite strain as follows:

$$\varepsilon_c = (n + 1 - \phi) \varepsilon_c^n + (\phi - n) \varepsilon_c^{n+1} \quad (10)$$

where n is the largest integer not higher than ϕ .

To find the stress-strain relation, an applied strain is first prescribed. Then, the crack densities in 0° and 90° plies are determined from Fig. 3. An iterative procedure is followed to determine the applied stress, σ_c , so that the evaluated strain from Eq. (10) is identical with the prescribed strain. Repeating the procedure results in the whole stress-strain curve.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The calculations are performed based upon the material properties of the SiC/CAS composite listed in Table 1, and the predicted critical stresses for matrix cracking are shown in Fig. 4. The numerical values of E_2 and α_2 are given by the rule-of-mixtures. The solutions at $d=0$ are actually those of the unidirectional composite. As the ratio d/b increases, both σ_{cr1} and σ_{cr2} decrease. The reason is that the matrix cracking modes are associated with major cracks, in which higher d/b ratios mean higher stress concentrations at the 0° -plies. For the SiC/CAS composite, σ_{cr2} is significantly lower than σ_{cr1} , indicating that fiber/matrix debonding occurs during matrix cracking. The experimental results of matrix cracking initiation are indicated by the solid circles; the stresses at which crack density reaches 95% of saturated density are indicated by open circles. As indicated, σ_{cr2} is closer to the experimental results. The fact that the theoretical predictions are higher than the experimental results may be due to the simplification of the model and the accuracy of the material properties used, especially τ_i and γ_m .

The predicted stress-strain relations for the $[0_3/90/0_3]$ and $[0_3/90_3/0_3]$ SiC/CAS composites are shown in Fig. 5. At strain levels smaller than 0.05%, no crack occurs, and the crack spacings can be considered as infinite, and the stress-strain curve is linear as can be seen from Eq. (7). Transverse cracks occur at about 0.09% for the $[0_3/90/0_3]$ and 0.07% for the $[0_3/90_3/0_3]$ composites. However, due to low crack densities, the stress-strain curves are virtually linear up to about 0.12% for the $[0_3/90/0_3]$ and 0.10% for the $[0_3/90_3/0_3]$ composites. As the applied strain further increases, the crack densities increase rapidly, and the stress-strain nonlinearity becomes more pronounced. The predicted stresses are higher than the experimental data; this is partly because of fiber damage in the composite, which has not been taken into account in this paper. However, the trends of the predicted curves agree with the experimental data.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Two closed-form solutions for the critical stress of matrix cracking have been obtained. For the SiC/CAS composite, σ_{cr2} is lower than σ_{cr1} , indicating that fiber/matrix debonding is likely to occur during matrix cracking. Both the experimental and predicted critical stresses decrease as the thickness of 90° plies increase.

The stress-strain relations for ϕ being integers have been obtained in closed-form solutions. Using the concept of interpolation, the composite stress-strain curves have been predicted. The initiation of

transverse cracks in 90° plies does not lead to a significant deviation of the curve from initial linearity; the nonlinearity becomes apparent only when the crack densities are high enough. The predicted results have been compared with experimental data for the [0₃/90/0₃] and [0₃/90₃/0₃] composites. The predicted results are higher than the experimental data, which may be due to fiber damage in the composites.

Acknowledgments

We wish to acknowledge the partial support of NASA-Lewis Research Center (TWC) (Dr. John P. Gyekenyesi, program director), and the Center for Composite Materials of University of Delaware (WSK).

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Table 1 Material Properties of the SiC/CAS Composite [8,10-12]

E_f (GPa)	210
E_m (GPa)	95.5
V_f	0.35
τ_i (MPa)	12.0
K_m (MPa·m ^{1/2})	2.2
γ_m (J/m ²)	25.3
r_o (μ m)	8.0
α_f (1/ $^{\circ}$ C)	3.1×10^{-6}
α_m (1/ $^{\circ}$ C)	4.5×10^{-6}
ΔT ($^{\circ}$ C)	-1000

Fig. 1 Damage configurations

Fig. 2 Matrix cracking in a major crack

Fig. 3 Crack densities in the 0° and 90° plies. (experimental data form Ref.8)

Fig. 4 Critical stresses for matrix cracking. (experimental data form Ref. 8)

Fig.5 Predicted and experimental results of the stress-strain curves. (experimental data form Ref.8)